

Extended comparisons of total power loss measurements performed by an SST using revised measurement procedures at room temperature

Extended final report

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1 Introduction

Two experimental setups are currently used for the measurement of power losses in magnetic steels – the Epstein frame and the Single Sheet Tester (SST). To date, a number of intercomparisons, promoted by EURAMET and the IEC TC 68 have confirmed good reproducibility for both the Epstein and SST methods, with an uncertainty around 1 % for the power loss measurement. These comparisons, however, were only focused on measurements at 50 Hz and room temperature [1].

Within the HEFMAG project a new reference round robin comparison was performed between Epstein frames and SST at 50 Hz and 100 Hz using non-oriented and grain-oriented samples. In addition, a new Epstein round robin comparison up to higher frequencies of 10 kHz using non-oriented and Fe₅₀Co₅₀ sheets was performed.

As an output of the round robin test a number of documents will be drafted in parallel to the conductance of the measurements. At all stages of the round robin test these documents shall reflect the current state of knowledge:

1. Report of measurement results: This document contains the results of measurements and their accuracy for each method and each laboratory and a discussion of the findings during the round robin comparison. This report will be shared through a report to IEC TC 68 and made available to the stakeholders.
2. A Good practice guide on the measurement of power losses in non-oriented steels and grain-oriented materials using standard measurement setups at room temperature will be developed for end users This document will provide the basis for discussions on CMC revisions and updates of some of the IEC 60404 standards within the IEC TC 68.

2 Reference samples

The aim of this comparison was to evaluate and reduce the uncertainty of SST loss measurements up to 100 Hz according to IEC 60404-3 and to provide new data concerning the behaviour of SST. The comparison was conducted using SST circuits made for standard samples with dimensions 500 mm × 500 mm.

Five SST samples were prepared for the comparison. The transfer standards are samples of grain-oriented (GO) and non-oriented (NO) electrical steel:

- two samples of NO steel sheets with dimensions 500×500 mm and a thickness of approximately 0.2 mm (NO 0.2) and 0.3 mm (NO 0.3). These samples were used for measurements at frequencies up to 100 Hz;
- three samples of GO steel sheets with dimensions 500×500 mm and a thickness of approximately 0.18 mm (GO 0.18), 0.2 mm (Laser Scribed 0.2) and 0.3 mm (GO 0.3). These samples were used for measurement from 50 Hz to 100 Hz.

All samples were demagnetized prior to measurement.

3 Measurements to be made

3.1 Quantity to be measured

Measurements of specific total power loss P_s (W/kg) of the SST samples were performed according to standard IEC 60404-3 (up to 100 Hz) using optimized experimental SST setups for power loss measurements under standard conditions.

The magnetic polarization J_m was measured at $H_m = 800$ A/m in the GO sheets and at $H_m = 2500$ A/m in the NO sheets at 50 Hz.

4 Organisation

4.1 Pilot Laboratory

Pilot laboratory:

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Laboratory of Electromagnetic Quantities
Michal Ulvr
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4.2 Participants

The following national metrology institutes (NMIs) and stakeholders participated the comparison:

Acronym	Laboratory	Country	Contact
INRIM	Istituto Nazionale di Ricerca Metrologica	Italy	Massimo Pasquale m.pasquale@inrim.it Carlo Appino c.appino@inrim.it
PTB	Physikalisch-Technische Bundesanstalt	Germany	Franziska Weickert franziska.weickert@ptb.de Korbinian Pfnuer korbinian.pfnuer@ptb.de
NPL	National Physical Laboratory	United Kingdom	Stuart Harmon stuart.harmon@npl.co.uk Daniel Brunt daniel.brunt@npl.co.uk

NIM	National Institute of Metrology	China	Wenjie Gong wjgong@nim.ac.cn
×	Baosteel	China	ZHOU Xing ZHOUXH@tunkia.com shenjie170498@baosteel.com
M-P	Magnet-Physik	Germany	Robert Hiergeist robert.hiergeist@magnet-physik.de
TK	ThyssenKrupp	Germany, France	Christian Hecht christian.hecht@thyssenkrupp.com

4.3 *Comparison schedule*

The comparison was carried out by a circulation scheme. The organization of the comparison follows: 1. INRIM, 2. PTB, 3. NPL and then the samples were returned to INRIM. After this round the samples were sent to NIM China and stakeholders Baosteel, Magnet-Physik and ThyssenKrupp.

Each participant covered the freight charges from his location to the next one in the list. Each participant was responsible for insurance of the samples from arrival in their laboratory until arrival in the subsequent laboratory.

The transport of the travelling standards was arranged by door-to-door parcel service.

5 **Measurement instructions**

5.1 *Measurements of the samples*

Each participant performed the following measurements using their standard equipment and measurement procedure. The specific total losses were measured stepwise from the lowest to the highest peak polarization value J_m given below at given frequencies. The measuring temperature was 23 ± 1 °C. If not, an appropriate correcting of the coefficient was applied.

Parameters for the SST NO samples	
frequency (Hz)	specific total power loss at J_m
50	1 T, 1.5 T
100	1 T, 1.5 T

Parameters for the SST GO samples	
frequency (Hz)	specific total power loss at J_m
50	1 T, 1.5 T, 1.7 T, 1.8
100	1 T, 1.5 T, 1.7 T, 1.8 T

6 Measurement results

6.1 Calculation of the reference value and its uncertainty

For all measurements of total losses and $J_m(H_m)$ measurements, the evaluation of this comparison was performed following procedure B in [2]. The Mandel-Paule (M-P) mean [3] was chosen for the analysis of the data. On its basis the following characteristics were calculated:

- the modified reduced observed chi-squared value by the formula:

$$\tilde{\chi}_{obs} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{N-1} \sum_{i=1}^N \frac{(x_i - x_{ref})^2}{u_i^2 + s^2}} \quad (1)$$

where N is the number of participants, x_i is the results of the total losses of the i -th participant of the comparisons and u_i is the declared standard uncertainty of the i -th participant of the comparison for coverage factor $k = 1$ (68%). The value of the unexplained variance s^2 is chosen such that chi-squared value < 1 and the expanded uncertainty of the reference value is $< 3\%$.

- the reference value of total losses x_{ref} by the formula:

$$x_{ref} = \mathbf{u}^2(x_{ref}) \sum_{i=1}^N \frac{x_i}{u_i^2 + s^2} \quad (2)$$

- standard uncertainty of the reference value of total losses $u(x_{ref})$ by the formula:

$$u(x_{ref}) = \left[\sum_{i=1}^N \frac{1}{u_i^2 + s^2} \right]^{-1/2} \quad (3)$$

- the degree of equivalence of the measurement standard d_i by the formula (4) with a corresponding uncertainty by the formulas (5), (6):

$$d_i = x_i - x_{ref} \quad (4)$$

$$u(d_i) = \sqrt{u^2(x_i) + u^2(x_{ref})} \quad (5)$$

$$E_n = \frac{|d_i|}{2u(d_i)}, \quad (6)$$

where d_i is degree of equivalence and $u(d_i)$ is the standard uncertainty of the degree of equivalence.

The declared uncertainties are judged as confirmed if equation $E_n < 1$ is satisfied, that is a confirmation of the relevant rows from CMC.

6.2 Evaluation of comparison results

In previous report “Comparisons of total power loss measurements performed by an SST using revised measurement procedures at room temperature - Final report” the results of NO samples were stated for both direction of magnetization (longitudinal and transversal). But some stakeholders results were stated only as average from both direction of magnetization. That’s why all results of NO samples are now stated as average in this report, which is main difference from previous report. Results of NMIs are marked as Lab1, Lab2, etc. and stakeholders results are marked as Stkh1, Stkh2, etc.

Parameters of measured samples:

Sample	Density (kg/m ³)	Cross section (mm ²)	Weight (kg)	Length L (m)	Width W (m)
Laser scribed GO 0.2	7650	93.571	0.35793	0.50003	×
GO 0.18	7650	87.823	0.33587	0.49992	×
NO 0.3	7600	147.28 (L)/147.17 (W)	0.5592	0.49959	0.49995
GO 0.3	7650	144.11	0.55161	0.50036	×
NO 0.2	7650	97.397 (L)/97.413 (W)	0.37244	0.49986	0.49978

6.2.1 Total losses results

Losses (average)	Lab1		Lab2		Lab3		Lab4		Stkh1		Stkh2		x_{ref} (W/kg)	$u(x_{ref})$ (W/kg)
	X	u_x , %	X	u_x , %	X	u_x , %	X	u_x , %	X	u_x , %	X	u_x , %		
$P_{1.0/50}$	0,9086	0,24	0,90915	0,28	0,906	0,85	0,888	0,50	0,8779	0,50	0,8955	0,06	0,8975	0,0091
$P_{1.5/50}$	2,189	0,24	2,19795	0,33	2,233	1,00	2,155	0,50	2,239	0,50	2,1618	0,15	2,195	0,021
$P_{1.0/100}$	2,1305	0,24	2,1337	0,27	2,114	0,85	2,088	0,50	2,078	0,50	2,1043	0,04	2,108	0,021
$P_{1.5/100}$	5,088	0,24	5,1345	0,34	5,278	1,00	5,020	0,50	5,080	0,50	5,1066	0,12	5,116	0,066

Losses (average)	d_i						$u(d_i)$						E_n					
	Lab1	Lab2	Lab3	Lab4	Stkh1	Stkh2	Lab1	Lab2	Lab3	Lab4	Stkh1	Stkh2	Lab1	Lab2	Lab3	Lab4	Stkh1	Stkh2
$P_{1.0/50}$	0.0111	0.0117	0.0085	-0.0095	-0.0196	-0.0020	0.019	0.019	0.024	0.020	0.020	0.018	0.588	0.614	0.356	0.467	0.969	0.109
$P_{1.5/50}$	-0.0058	0.0032	0.0377	-0.0398	0.0442	-0.0330	0.043	0.044	0.061	0.047	0.047	0.042	0.134	0.071	0.616	0.845	0.931	0.779
$P_{1.0/100}$	0.0224	0.0256	0.0059	-0.0206	-0.0301	-0.0038	0.043	0.043	0.055	0.047	0.046	0.042	0.522	0.593	0.106	0.444	0.648	0.092
$P_{1.5/100}$	-0.0276	0.0189	0.1624	-0.0956	-0.0361	-0.0090	0.135	0.137	0.169	0.142	0.142	0.133	0.205	0.138	0.959	0.675	0.255	0.068

Results of the NO 0.3 sample

Losses (average)	Lab1		Lab2		Lab3		Lab4		Stkh1		x_{ref} (W/kg)	$u(x_{ref})$ (W/kg)
	X	u_x , %	X	u_x , %	X	u_x , %	X	u_x , %	X	u_x , %		
$P_{1.0/50}$	0.9545	0.24	0.9583	0.28	0.950	1.10	0.932	0.50	0.9299	0.13	0.9447	0.0075
$P_{1.5/50}$	2.2745	0.38	2.28475	0.33	2.283	1.15	2.253	0.50	2.2458	0.21	2.266	0.010
$P_{1.0/100}$	2.101	0.24	2.1131	0.27	2.080	0.85	2.053	0.50	2.0536	0.04	2.080	0.017
$P_{1.5/100}$	4.973	0.25	5.042	0.34	5.100	1.00	4.939	0.50	4.9987	0.16	5.006	0.038

Losses (average)	d_i					$u(d_i)$					E_n				
	Lab1	Lab2	Lab3	Lab4	Stkh1	Lab1	Lab2	Lab3	Lab4	Stkh1	Lab1	Lab2	Lab3	Lab4	Stkh1
$P_{1.0/50}$	0.0098	0.0136	0.0053	-0.0127	-0.0148	0.016	0.016	0.026	0.018	0.015	0.624	0.854	0.205	0.722	0.978
$P_{1.5/50}$	0.0084	0.0186	0.0169	-0.0136	-0.0203	0.027	0.025	0.056	0.030	0.023	0.312	0.731	0.299	0.447	0.899
$P_{1.0/100}$	0.0207	0.0328	-0.0003	-0.0273	-0.0267	0.035	0.035	0.049	0.039	0.033	0.595	0.934	0.007	0.699	0.803
$P_{1.5/100}$	-0.0330	0.0360	0.0935	-0.0675	-0.0073	0.079	0.082	0.127	0.090	0.077	0.417	0.438	0.739	0.751	0.095

Results of the NO 0.2 sample

Losses	Lab1		Lab2		Lab3		Lab4		Stkh1		Stkh2		Stkh3		x_{ref} (W/kg)	$u(x_{ref})$ (W/kg)
	X	$u_x, \%$	X	$u_x, \%$	X	$u_x, \%$	X	$u_x, \%$	X	$u_x, \%$	X	$u_x, \%$	X	$u_x, \%$		
$P_{1.0/50}$	0.2010	0.20	0.2023	0.29	0.201	0.65	0.201	0.50	0.2092	0.15	0.210	0.50	0.205	0.50	0.2042	0.0030
$P_{1.5/50}$	0.4915	0.20	0.4906	0.30	0.486	0.60	0.485	0.50	0.4995	0.09	0.498	0.50	0.491	0.50	0.4917	0.0042
$P_{1.7/50}$	0.693	0.28	0.6916	0.34	0.680	0.75	0.685	0.50	0.7043	0.06	0.703	0.50	0.697	0.50	0.6936	0.0054
$P_{1.8/50}$	0.884	0.38	0.8835	0.34	0.865	1.20	0.874	0.50	0.8989	0.36	0.896	0.50	0.894	0.50	0.8859	0.0060
$P_{1.0/100}$	0.5793	0.20	0.5822	0.29	0.576	0.65	0.573	0.50	0.5968	0.15	×	×	0.588	0.50	0.5826	0.0074
$P_{1.5/100}$	1.381	0.20	1.3784	0.29	1.357	0.60	1.360	0.50	1.3995	0.15	×	×	1.378	0.50	1.3763	0.0085
$P_{1.7/100}$	1.891	0.28	×	×	1.843	0.75	1.863	0.50	1.91810	0.130	1.935	0.50	1.895	0.50	1.891	0.021
$P_{1.8/100}$	2.337	0.38	×	×	2.276	1.20	2.303	0.50	2.37380	0.240	2.368	0.50	2.359	0.50	2.339	0.017

Losses	d_i							$u(d_i)$							E_n						
	Lab1	Lab2	Lab3	Lab4	Stkh1	Stkh2	Stkh3	Lab1	Lab2	Lab3	Lab4	Stkh1	Stkh2	Stkh3	Lab1	Lab2	Lab3	Lab4	Stkh1	Stkh2	Stkh3
$P_{1.0/50}$	-0.0032	-0.0019	-0.0032	-0.0032	0.0050	0.0058	0.0008	0.006	0.006	0.007	0.006	0.006	0.006	0.006	0.525	0.310	0.486	0.502	0.814	0.898	0.122
$P_{1.5/50}$	-0.0002	-0.0011	-0.0057	-0.0067	0.0078	0.0063	-0.0007	0.009	0.009	0.010	0.010	0.009	0.010	0.010	0.025	0.125	0.556	0.689	0.915	0.640	0.073
$P_{1.7/50}$	-0.0006	-0.0020	-0.0136	-0.0086	0.0107	0.0094	0.0034	0.012	0.012	0.015	0.013	0.011	0.013	0.013	0.053	0.170	0.914	0.671	0.982	0.726	0.263
$P_{1.8/50}$	-0.0019	-0.0024	-0.0209	-0.0119	0.0130	0.0101	0.0081	0.014	0.013	0.024	0.015	0.014	0.015	0.015	0.138	0.178	0.872	0.803	0.958	0.677	0.544
$P_{1.0/100}$	-0.0033	-0.0004	-0.0066	-0.0096	0.0142	×	0.0054	0.015	0.015	0.017	0.016	0.015	×	0.016	0.220	0.027	0.398	0.604	0.950	×	0.338
$P_{1.5/100}$	0.0047	0.0021	-0.0193	-0.0163	0.0232	×	0.0017	0.018	0.019	0.023	0.022	0.017	×	0.022	0.265	0.113	0.821	0.750	1.331	×	0.078
$P_{1.7/100}$	-0.0003	×	-0.0483	-0.0283	0.0268	0.0437	0.0037	0.043	×	0.050	0.045	0.042	0.046	0.046	0.007	×	0.969	0.622	0.642	0.955	0.081
$P_{1.8/100}$	-0.0022	×	-0.0632	-0.0362	0.0346	0.0288	0.0198	0.039	×	0.065	0.041	0.036	0.042	0.042	0.057	×	0.978	0.873	0.953	0.688	0.474

Results of the GO 0.18 sample

Losses	Lab1		Lab2		Lab3		Lab4		Stkh1		Stkh2		Stkh3		x_{ref} (W/kg)	$u(x_{ref})$ (W/kg)
	X	$u_x, \%$	X	$u_x, \%$	X	$u_x, \%$	X	$u_x, \%$	X	$u_x, \%$	X	$u_x, \%$	X	$u_x, \%$		
$P_{1.0/50}$	0.3456	0.20	0.3417	0.29	0.342	0.65	0.335	0.50	0.3495	0.20	0.343	0.50	0.343	0.50	0.3429	0.0038
$P_{1.5/50}$	0.773	0.20	0.768	0.29	0.767	0.60	×	×	0.7746	0.10	0.773	0.50	0.764	0.50	0.7704	0.0024
$P_{1.7/50}$	1.043	0.28	1.0384	0.32	1.033	0.75	×	×	1.0387	0.13	1.036	0.50	1.029	0.50	1.0374	0.0026
$P_{1.8/50}$	1.285	0.38	1.2784	0.40	1.257	1.20	×	×	1.2731	0.14	1.265	0.50	1.270	0.50	1.2736	0.0041
$P_{1.0/100}$	1.054	0.20	1.0436	0.27	1.035	0.65	×	×	1.0523	0.05	1.055	0.50	1.037	0.50	1.0471	0.0036
$P_{1.5/100}$	2.332	0.20	2.3069	0.29	×	×	×	×	2.3097	0.08	2.320	0.50	2.282	0.50	2.311	0.012

Losses	d_i							$u(d_i)$							E_n						
	Lab1	Lab2	Lab3	Lab4	Stkh1	Stkh2	Stkh3	Lab1	Lab2	Lab3	Lab4	Stkh1	Stkh2	Stkh3	Lab1	Lab2	Lab3	Lab4	Stkh1	Stkh2	Stkh3
$P_{1.0/50}$	0.0027	-0.0012	-0.0009	-0.0079	0.0066	0.0001	0.0001	0.008	0.008	0.009	0.008	0.008	0.008	0.008	0.353	0.147	0.097	0.942	0.855	0.017	0.017
$P_{1.5/50}$	0.0026	-0.0024	-0.0038	×	0.0042	0.0026	-0.0064	0.006	0.006	0.010	×	0.005	0.009	0.009	0.462	0.371	0.366	×	0.848	0.287	0.714
$P_{1.7/50}$	0.0056	0.0010	-0.0047	×	0.0013	-0.0014	-0.0084	0.008	0.008	0.016	×	0.006	0.012	0.012	0.715	0.120	0.287	×	0.223	0.119	0.726
$P_{1.8/50}$	0.0114	0.0048	-0.0170	×	-0.0005	-0.0086	-0.0036	0.013	0.013	0.031	×	0.009	0.015	0.015	0.895	0.367	0.544	×	0.056	0.571	0.238
$P_{1.0/100}$	0.0069	-0.0035	-0.0118	×	0.0052	0.0079	-0.0101	0.008	0.009	0.015	×	0.007	0.013	0.013	0.819	0.380	0.771	×	0.705	0.616	0.796
$P_{1.5/100}$	0.0213	-0.0038	×	×	-0.0010	0.0093	-0.0287	0.025	0.027	×	×	0.024	0.033	0.033	0.844	0.140	×	×	0.042	0.282	0.877

Results of the GO 0.3 sample

Losses (average)	Lab1		Lab2		Lab3		Lab4		Stkh1		Stkh2		x_{ref} (W/kg)	$u(x_{ref})$ (W/kg)
	X	u_x , %	X	u_x , %	X	u_x , %	X	u_x , %	X	u_x , %	X	u_x , %		
$P_{1.0/50}$	0.2246	0.20	0.22465	0.30	0.224	0.65	0.223	0.50	0.2305	0.50	0.2310	0.15	0.2262	0.0025
$P_{1.5/50}$	0.5349	0.20	0.5359	0.32	0.529	0.60	0.527	0.50	0.538	0.50	0.5399	0.12	0.5342	0.0034
$P_{1.7/50}$	0.754	0.28	0.7552	0.34	0.742	0.75	0.741	0.50	0.754	0.50	0.7575	0.09	0.7511	0.0039
$P_{1.8/50}$	0.955	0.38	0.9564	0.46	0.936	1.20	0.934	0.50	0.951	0.50	0.9548	0.21	0.9487	0.0061
$P_{1.0/100}$	0.6632	0.20	0.6608	0.30	0.656	0.65	0.652	0.50	0.675	0.50	0.6789	0.09	0.6644	0.0074
$P_{1.5/100}$	1.544	0.20	1.5356	0.29	1.513	0.60	1.516	0.50	1.541	0.50	1.5537	0.08	1.535	0.010
$P_{1.7/100}$	2.099	0.28	×	×	2.045	0.75	2.062	0.50	2.085	0.50	2.1051	0.080	2.081	0.014
$P_{1.8/100}$	2.566	0.38	×	×	2.505	1.20	2.510	0.50	2.539	0.50	2.5639	0.120	2.541	0.015

Losses	d_i						$u(d_i)$						E_n					
	Lab1	Lab2	Lab3	Lab4	Stkh1	Stkh2	Lab1	Lab2	Lab3	Lab4	Stkh1	Stkh2	Lab1	Lab2	Lab3	Lab4	Stkh1	Stkh2
$P_{1.0/50}$	-0.0016	-0.0016	-0.0027	-0.0032	0.0043	0.0048	0.005	0.005	0.006	0.005	0.005	0.005	0.325	0.309	0.465	0.596	0.779	0.951
$P_{1.5/50}$	0.0007	0.0017	-0.0055	-0.0072	0.0038	0.0057	0.007	0.008	0.009	0.009	0.009	0.007	0.094	0.220	0.593	0.843	0.436	0.823
$P_{1.7/50}$	0.0029	0.0041	-0.0092	-0.0101	0.0029	0.0064	0.009	0.009	0.014	0.011	0.011	0.008	0.324	0.436	0.675	0.939	0.265	0.804
$P_{1.8/50}$	0.0063	0.0077	-0.0124	-0.0147	0.0022	0.0061	0.014	0.015	0.026	0.015	0.016	0.013	0.441	0.509	0.485	0.956	0.141	0.472
$P_{1.0/100}$	-0.0012	-0.0036	-0.0087	-0.0124	0.0108	0.0145	0.015	0.015	0.017	0.016	0.016	0.015	0.078	0.232	0.510	0.762	0.663	0.974
$P_{1.5/100}$	0.0095	0.0011	-0.0215	-0.0185	0.0065	0.0192	0.021	0.022	0.027	0.025	0.025	0.020	0.452	0.052	0.793	0.730	0.257	0.945
$P_{1.7/100}$	0.0181	×	-0.0358	-0.0189	0.0041	0.0242	0.031	×	0.042	0.035	0.035	0.028	0.594	×	0.859	0.541	0.117	0.854

Results of the Laser scribed GO 0.2 sample

6.2.2 $J_m(H_m)$ curve results at 50 Hz

H_m (A/m) (longitudinal direction)	Lab1		Lab2		Lab3		x_{ref} (T)	$u(x_{ref})$ (T)	d_i			$u(d_i)$			E_n		
	X	u_x , %	X	u_x , %	X	u_x , %			Lab1	Lab2	Lab3	Lab1	Lab2	Lab3	Lab1	Lab2	Lab3
2500	1.5550	0.23	1.5632	0.07	1.556	0.23	1.5590	0.0028	-0.004	0.004	-0.003	0.009	0.006	0.009	0.441	0.697	0.331

H_m (A/m) (transver- sal direc- tion)	Lab1		Lab2		Lab3		x_{ref} (T)	$u(x_{ref})$ (T)	d_i			$u(d_i)$			E_n		
	X	u_x , %	X	u_x , %	X	u_x , %			Lab1	Lab2	Lab3	Lab1	Lab2	Lab3	Lab1	Lab2	Lab3
2500	1.507	0.23	1.513	0.08	1.507	0.23	1.5102	0.0023	-0.003	0.003	-0.003	0.008	0.005	0.008	0.386	0.617	0.386

Results of the NO 0.3 sample

H_m (A/m) (longitudinal direction)	Lab1		Lab2		Lab3		x_{ref} (T)	$u(x_{ref})$ (T)	d_i			$u(d_i)$			E_n		
	X	u_x , %	X	u_x , %	X	u_x , %			Lab1	Lab2	Lab3	Lab1	Lab2	Lab3	Lab1	Lab2	Lab3
2500	1.563	0.23	1.571	0.06	1.563	0.35	1.5671	0.0029	-0.004	0.004	-0.004	0.009	0.006	0.012	0.441	0.631	0.330

H_m (A/m) (transver- sal direc- tion)	Lab1		Lab2		Lab3		x_{ref} (T)	$u(x_{ref})$ (T)	d_i			$u(d_i)$			E_n		
	X	u_x , %	X	u_x , %	X	u_x , %			Lab1	Lab2	Lab3	Lab1	Lab2	Lab3	Lab1	Lab2	Lab3
2500	1.522	0.23	1.527	0.06	1.523	0.23	1.5253	0.0017	-0.003	0.002	-0.002	0.008	0.004	0.008	0.425	0.427	0.297

Results of the NO 0.2 sample

H_m (A/m)	Lab1		Lab2		Lab3		x_{ref} (T)	$u(x_{ref})$ (T)	d_i			$u(d_i)$			E_n		
	X	u_x , %	X	u_x , %	X	u_x , %			Lab1	Lab2	Lab3	Lab1	Lab2	Lab3	Lab1	Lab2	Lab3
800	1.8850	0.23	1.8887	0.06	1.885	0.23	1.8867	0.0035	-0.002	0.002	-0.002	0.011	0.007	0.011	0.152	0.277	0.152

Results of the GO 0.18 sample

H_m (A/m)	Lab1		Lab2		Lab3		x_{ref} (T)	$u(x_{ref})$ (T)	d_i			$u(d_i)$			E_n		
	X	u_x , %	X	u_x , %	X	u_x , %			Lab1	Lab2	Lab3	Lab1	Lab2	Lab3	Lab1	Lab2	Lab3
800	1.893	0.23	1.902	0.06	1.893	0.23	1.8971	0.0035	-0.004	0.005	-0.004	0.011	0.007	0.011	0.368	0.673	0.368

Results of the GO 0.3 sample

H_m (A/m)	Lab1		Lab2		Lab3		x_{ref} (T)	$u(x_{ref})$ (T)	d_i			$u(d_i)$			E_n		
	X	u_x , %	X	u_x , %	X	u_x , %			Lab1	Lab2	Lab3	Lab1	Lab2	Lab3	Lab1	Lab2	Lab3
800	1.891	0.23	1.8992	0.07	1.891	0.23	1.8951	0.0030	-0.004	0.004	-0.004	0.011	0.007	0.011	0.386	0.636	0.386

Results of the Laser scribed GO 0.2 sample

NO 0.3_long

NO 0.3_trans

NO 0.2_long

NO 0.2_trans

GO 0.18

GO 0.3

7 Summary and conclusions

After the evaluation of the data in agreement with the rules of EURAMET the agreement of the comparison is very good, because E_n values smaller than 1 are obtained for all data points. This report also confirmed that the results are consistent with the declared uncertainty.

8 References

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